

Legal Provisions Governing Administrative Appeal Against The Decision To Estimate The Tax

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: October 13, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: May 14, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Legal, Administrative, Economic, Tax</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6547632</p>	<p><i>The research examined the legal provisions governing the administrative challenge to the decision to estimate the tax because the subject is of extensive importance in its procedural aspect, since the permanent change in tax laws requires the legislator to keep up with the economic transformations by amending the texts and the year for others, as well as ambiguity in some legal texts that need to be clarified and clarified, and to highlight the direction of the tax legislator from some judicial procedures, in addition to determining the methods of estimating the tax base, and indicating the methods of taxation, part To be my research in this area so that taxes are not a heavy burden on society with its various elements, and for the purpose of studying the subject of research and addressing the problem at hand, we divided the research into three investigations, including the first research of the study, what is the estimate of tax, while we will deal in the second research, decisions that can be administratively challenged in tax legislation, while we reviewed in the third research, the procedural framework for administrative challenge to tax assessment decisions down to conclusion and what It will contain findings and recommendations, as well as a list of sources and references.</i></p>

Introduction

In order not to be a significant burden on society in its various elements, and to play its effective role in the State, taxes must be enacted to ensure that, and the tax law of the tax administration has arranged privileges, rights, and methods to access the taxable material, accurately decide the amount of its debt, impose obligations to ensure that its rights are preserved and its debts are fulfilled, and in return impose sanctions on anyone who obstructs the administration's use of these rights, and gives it broad freedom to collect evidence and information. Statements and discussion of the taxpayer to reveal the amount of the tax pot, to seek to reach the reality of the tax pot, chanting it and collecting it as realistically as possible, especially since the State is the strongest party in the tax relationship because of its authority and sovereignty, with the administration obliged to ensure in that process two conflicting interests, the first of which is the interest of the party in charge, the second is the interest of the State.

From the above, the tax has two main aspects. The first is that it is a general revenue for the state that is of general benefit, and the second is a financial mandate for those concerned to pay it. It is therefore self-evident that the parties to this relationship do not meet and agree in all cases, hence the dispute and dispute in the tax area. The Iraqi legislator has developed an important set of special texts, to resolve and resolve this type of dispute, which is characterized by a kind of difficulty and complexity, given the dispersal and dispersal of its provisions through different texts, The tax legislator was therefore granted the right to defend himself and his money by objecting and challenging the tax discretionary decisions of the tax authority.

Significant of the study

The subject of the research is of extensive importance, particularly in its procedural aspect, as the constant change of tax laws requires the legislator to keep pace with economic transformations by amending texts and enacting them to others, which has led to a lack of knowledge of them by tax officials, as well as the ambiguity of some of these legal texts, which need to be explained and clarified more. In addition, the direction of the tax legislator is highlighted by some of the judicial procedures used to settle this dispute in comparison with the general rules. The study is also of other importance, reflected in the determination of the methods and accuracy of the tax base estimate, as well as the methods of estimating the tax place.

The problem of the study

The problem in our study is the fact that the tax pot is the source through which the state deducts various taxes, and the failure and overestimation of the tax have negative effects. Overvaluation increases the burden on individuals in society, which leads them to evade, cheat or even stop their activities. On the other hand, failure to estimate wastes the tax authority's access to financial resources sought by the Treasury. The State,

considering that the volume of tax revenues is closely linked to the tax pot, the problem of studying is therefore crystallized in answering the main question:

What is the legal nature of the methods and mechanisms for challenging tax assessment decisions?

From this problem, the following questions arise:

1. What are the methods used to estimate the tax place?
2. What is the nature and legal basis of the appeal phase of the tax decision?
3. What is the nature of the competent body to consider challenging the estimate of the tax base?
4. What are the administrative appeals procedures for tax assessment decisions?

Objective reasons

The desire to state the mechanism of estimating the tax base and how it is estimated and to challenge these tax decisions provided for in Iraqi legislation and comparative legislation by reviewing the provisions of that tax legislation. To highlight parties that have the right to object and challenge decisions to assess the tax, to determine who may object, and to clarify the objections granted by law to the conflicting parties, by following up on the provisions of Iraqi tax legislation and the provisions of jurisprudence and the judiciary. Highlight the nature of the appeal phase of the tax decision, as well as the administrative appeals procedures in tax assessment decisions.

Personal reasons

Our inclinations on this subject and a desire to increase knowledge attainment in this area, given the importance of the subject and the motivation to provide additional studies, in line with economic and social changes. Lack of sufficient research in this area and a desire to expand and enrich my knowledge in this area to facilitate integration into professional life. In this study, we will rely on the descriptive and analytical approach: to limit some phenomena and collect information from their various sources and then subjecting them to scrutiny and analysis to the results, by explaining and analyzing the legal provisions governing the methods of estimating and challenging the tax under tax legislation in Iraqi law and comparative legislation, where we have used a range of judicial rulings, decisions and jurisprudence.

To study the subject of the research and address the problem at hand, we divided the subject of the study into three investigations, including the first research the study, what is the estimate of the tax, while in the second research we will address the decisions that can be challenged administratively in the tax legislation, while we reviewed in the third research, the procedural framework for the administrative challenge of tax assessment decisions, to the conclusion and the results and recommendations it will contain.

The first topic

What is the tax estimate?

The Law imposes several obligations on financiers to enable the administration or the relevant entity to determine the tax vessel and then verify its requirements and regulate its collection, in addition to preventing evasion, and it is recognized that these obligations must be mentioned specifically within the law, and if you mention the financier's commitment to it without the need for the administration to alert him to this, perhaps the most important of which is to file a declaration

To determine the importance of the above, we will divide this research into two demands, which we will address in the first requirement: the concept of the tax base, while dealing with the second requirement: the constitutional guarantees of the taxpayer in the area of tax assessment.

The first requirement: The concept of the tax base

The term tax base raises several technical and legal problems, which are not limited to the doctrinal aspects of defining the implications of the tax base or putting an end to disputes and problems where it is faithful to the meaning of the tax base. To arrive at a precise definition of the tax vessel, this requirement must be divided into two branches, which we address in section one: the definition of the tax base, while in the second section: methods of estimating the tax base.

Section one

Introducing the tax sink

Jurisprudence defines the tax base as:^[1] Where everyone differs in determining the meaning of money or that income that we have mentioned, it embodies the pot for each tax, so many disputes are closely related to the tax sink. When the interpretation of the meaning of the tax base expands the dispute between the financier and the tax administration, the large income means that the size of the tax is higher and larger, without a doubt reducing the resolution of the owners of large capital in the Investing it, reducing the amount of money invested in the country and raising tax evasion rates ^[2].

Determining the tax requires that the tax base be precisely defined, and the legal definition of the meaning of the tax base is a duty when interpreting tax laws, even if that money has another meaning in other laws.

Based on the above, the tax base is defined as: "The money specified by law is a source of a particular tax, which adds the type of money imposed by the tax on the occasion of its tax, the tax from which the income comes from is called income tax, which comes from real estate (real estate tax) and tax levied on the occasion of your initiation of money (consumption tax)". It should be noted that the Iraqi legislator did not address the

definition of the tax base, but referred only to taxable income, while taxable sources of income could be classified into three main sources: labor income, capital income, and mixed-income generated by the synergy of work and capital.

Section two

Methods of estimating the tax base

The origin of the tax is that it includes anyone who has the right to use the public services provided by the State, whether he or she resides on its territory or owns its land, property in which it generates income, whether it is a citizen or a foreigner, whether residing in or outside the State. Thus, the methods of determining the tax base are as follows [\[4\]](#):

The method of pre-determining the tax (distributional tax): In the distribution tax, the legislator merely determines the total amount to be collected from the individuals subject to it as a particular tax, after which the executive branch divides the burden of this tax on the taxpayers regardless of the income they receive [\[5\]](#). Due to the flaws in this method, most notably the lack of justice, most of the tax legislation in the world has left. How to determine the proportional tax rate and progressive tax: According to this method, the legislator determines the tax rate, i.e. determines the percentage of the article in place of the tax paid by the taxpayer, and then the value of the taxable material changes as the tax proceeds change and generally characterized by the expansion of the area of tax justice that may not be achieved previously, but the area of tax justice according to this method varies in the case of proportional tax from it upwards. [\[6\]](#):

First: Proportional tax: The tax is relative if its price does not change by changing the value of the subject matter, i.e. its price is fixed, such as a tax on commercial or industrial profits at a price (10%), and here the percentage of the amount deducted as a fixed tax no matter how much the proportion of these profits changes, but this method is meant to be unfair and its outcome is low, the higher the level of income of the individual charged with the higher the estimated tax receipt, but the more criticism on this tax demands the introduction of tax Progressive, particularly in capitalist states [\[7\]](#).

Second: Progressive tax: The tax is progressive if the price increases by the tax place, for example, a general revenue tax should be imposed at a price (10%) dinars on the first millennium of the taxpayer's income, and (15%) on the second millennium and so on. The relative tax receipt increases as the amount of the material in question increase, and in return the progressive tax result rises by a higher percentage than the rate of rising of the article imposed on it. [\[8\]](#) The measure must also be distinguished, as the upward price method of the layers divides the taxable substance income or capital into more than one layer, where the first starts from zero and ends at a certain point, from which the class after which, each layer is charged one price, It increases as we move from one layer to another, and despite the simplicity and ease with which the tax amount is determined, it is flawed by its distance from tax justice to subject income that exceeds the upper-class limit to the price set for the next layer, whatever the increase.

The second requirement: Constitutional guarantees for the taxpayer in the area of tax assessment

Constitutional guarantees in the tax area are the rules that the legislator is required to observe when assessing and imposing taxes, and their importance lies in the need to reconcile the interests of the person in charge and the State. The tax justice rule achieves social, economic, and financial objectives, so anyone who contributes to tax legalization cannot ignore the objectives and considerations of justice and equality, as the basis of the law is justice. From the above, we will divide this requirement into two branches: section 1: the objective constitutional guarantees of the tax-charged, and the second: the procedural constitutional guarantees of the tax-charged.

Section one

Objective constitutional guarantees for the tax-payer

One of the most important foundations for achieving the principles of justice and equal tax assessment is the legality of taxes, in the sense that it does not impose, amends, and exempt from tax except by law, and one of the most important things that achieve justice and equality in tax assessment decisions is: the tax should be imposed only by the text of a law issued by the competent authority of legislation, and the determination of those charged with such taxes, the determination of their amount and methods of collection [\[9\]](#).

However, it is not enough to pass a particular tax law until it is obligatory for individuals to be subject to the State treasury, as it lays the general foundations that apply and are imposed on each taxpayer, especially if the conditions for its imposition are met.

Accordingly, the jurisprudence differed on the duration of this tax debt, in part, he considered that the tax debt was based on the availability of the tax-generating incident, which the law required to be available, while another direction of jurisprudence considered that the obligation to taxes arises only if the administration takes certain decisions, the most important example of which is the audit decisions issued by the tax auditor, which include the name and number of the taxpayer, the duration of the tax and the rules on which the audit is based and the amount of tax.

Accordingly, both sides agree that the moment when a tax incident arises is the moment when the applicable law is determined in terms of the amount or scope of taxation, therefore, only the law determines the tax debt and appoints it as a negative appointment in terms of persons, place and time, and the financial authority's task in tax assessment is not to create this debt but to reveal it, it exists regardless of the will of both the taxpayer and the financial authority.

Within the course of Iraqi legislation, the legislation in the 2005 Iraqi Constitution stipulated that:

First, taxes and fees are not imposed, amended, levied, and exempted only by law.

Secondly, low-income earners are exempt from taxes, ensuring that the minimum living requirement is not violated, regulated by law. We conclude from the text of the previous article that the tax is not amended and abolished only by a provision of law, and therefore the provisions of this law must be changed whenever the interests of the community require it. The prevailing idea in France is that taxes are imposed only based on law, and therefore have now increased in France to depart from the principle of tax legality, by delegating parliament its power to legalize the government, so that the government has the right to amend the tax.

Tax exemption: The distinction must be made between tax exemption and non-entitlement to that tax, and from a legal point of view, the non-entitlement of the tax to a person means that the conditions imposed by law for the imposition of such a tax do not exist with that person, for example, a person who owns a property or a home in which he or she lives, who is not subject to the rental tax of the property ([11]).

Concerning tax exemption, the conditions for taxing a person required by law are available and are obliged to pay it, but the legislator intervenes to impose an exception to the payment of such tax in whole or in part for social, economic or political considerations, and therefore the exemption of any costly person from tax without legal provision by the financial authority constitutes a breach of the principle of tax law and an violation of the principle of the rule of law.

First: The rules of procedure of the Iraqi Parliament provided for the formation of several committees, including the Finance Committee, and provided for its terms of reference:

Second: proposing legislation on customs, taxes and fees.

Third: Follow-up the financial policy of various ministries and state institutions.

The Council's rules of procedure also stated: "Each committee must report to the Council on each subject referred to it, and the report must include its actions and reasons on which it was based, attach the texts of the projects or legislation in question to the report and its explanatory notes, and the report must include dissenting opinions that may have been expressed by its members on the subject).It also stipulated that when considering bills, each member should propose amendment, deletion, addition or fragmentation of the texts of the articles ([13]).

All these texts show that tax legislation passes through several channels through which parliament exercises a political role as guarantor of the rights of taxpayers, where citizens cannot be charged with or exempted from tax or amended by increase or decrease except by a law issued by the legislature. The Iraqi Parliament also has parliamentary control over the performance of the executive branch in its economic and financial policy, and this control constitutes a kind of political control guaranteed by the constitution to the legislative authority over the council of ministers, where the Iraqi constitution and the rules of procedures and mechanisms of the Iraqi Parliament regulated the procedures and mechanisms of this control ([14]).

The rules of procedure of the House of Representatives stipulate that the powers of the House of Representatives shall be regulated by the constitutional texts above, and based on these powers the House of Representatives exercises its work with oversight by asking the parliamentary question or questioning and then withdrawing confidence.[15].

based on all these procedures, the Minister of Finance, the Tax Director or any official of the General Tax Authority remains under the consideration, control and accountability of members of Parliament, thereby guaranteeing the rights of the taxpayer in the tax area and constitutes political protection against the risk of government abuse. It should be noted that the Iraqi constitutional texts have ensured an active oversight role for the Iraqi parliament in all areas, including the tax area, but the Iraqi parliament has not exercised its oversight role effectively, which has caused the government to take control of this area, so we can say, the oversight role of the Iraqi parliament is almost broken, which has been reflected in the deterioration of government performance in all areas, including the tax area, in a way that exposes the rights of those charged to waste and manipulation.

The second topic

Administrative challenge to tax legislation

Most tax legislation sought to grant the taxpayer the right to challenge the tax assessment administratively before the tax administration before resorting to the judiciary, and tax justice requires that individuals have the opportunity to challenge and challenge decisions and according to more than one stage, the most important of which may provoke the individual and lead him to seek ways and means to challenge them, are tax assessment

decisions, because these decisions represent an infringement of the income and money of the individual, and the Iraqi legislator did not look for others. From legislators, the taxpayer was given the right to object to discretionary income tax decisions in accordance with the provisions of the law. To expand the importance of the above, we will divide our research into two demands: administratively challengeable decisions in Iraqi tax legislation, and the second requirement: legal adaptation of decisions to challenge tax estimates.

The first requirement: Decisions subject to administrative challenge in Iraqi tax legislation

Tax immunities have a purely administrative nature despite their financial characteristics, which requires the existence of technical and administrative expertise for the members of the competent authority to adjudicate such disputes, because of their role in maintaining a balance between two contradictory interests, namely the interest of the individual and the interest of the State, and therefore a competent independent body must be identified so that the jurisdiction assigned to them is in line with the nature of those disputes, to reconcile those interests. To that end, the Iraqi legislature has set administrative committees chaired by a judge to adjudicate tax disputes, and Iraqi tax legislation has defined decisions subject to objection and appeal before these committees, so we will divide this requirement into two branches, as follows: Section one : Direct Tax Disputes, Section two : Indirect Tax Disputes.

Section one

Direct tax disputes

Direct taxes include income tax and property tax, and the provisions of both taxes have been regulated by a special law, to which certain jurisdictions are identified for considering tax disputes that occur when applying its provisions, and we will show this as follows:

The Iraqi legislator organized the means of objection in the income tax law in three stages: ⁽¹⁷⁾

First: The first stage is to object to the financial authority concerned, and the second is to object to appeals committees, while the last stage is to appeal to the discriminatory body, but about the subject of objection, it is limited to all matters relating to income assessment and tax only, and therefore objections whose subject matter does not relate to the amount of income and tax, the Iraqi legislator has expressly prevented objections to them to be outside the jurisdiction of those committees.

Second: The Iraqi legislator did not deviate from the direction he followed in the income tax law, in the law of the property tax by determining the ways to object to the decisions of the financial authority, which is in two stages, the first phase related to the taxpayer, as the law authorized the person in charge of the objection before the audit committees to demand a review of the estimate made by the assessment committees after several conditions are met, the objection is submitted within 30 days of the date of reporting the tax estimate and the taxpayer pays half of the amount of tax due within one month of The date of submission of the objection and where the decision of the assessment committee is final.

Third: The Iraqi legislator authorized the person in charge of challenging the decisions of the audit committee before the Real Estate Tax Office within one month of the date of notification, and the law authorized the Financial Authority to object to the decisions of the Audit Committee within one month of the date of notification, and the Diwan has the power to cancel, amend or support the decision and where its decision is outright ⁽¹⁸⁾.

Section two

Indirect tax disputes

Customs taxes and trading taxes are among the most prominent indirect taxes, and the Iraqi legislator has dealt with disputes due to the application of customs law and the land registration law by assigning the consideration of these disputes to certain entities, and where we will explain the competence of these entities as follows:

First: Disputes under customs law: The Iraqi legislator has identified competent bodies, such as the objection authority, the customs court, and the discriminatory body. It also specified the jurisdiction of the objection body to consider the objections of the person in charge against decisions taken by the Customs Service relating to the specifications and value of the goods within seven days of the date of notification, and in fact, the objection to these matters is an objection to the amount of tax, as the cases mentioned are considered determinants of the tax base, and contribute to the estimate of the price of the goods and thus determine the amount of tax payable ⁽¹⁹⁾. The Iraqi legislator has also been granted the power to hear disputes of a criminal nature, including smuggling offenses relating to claims filed by the Customs Administration against the customs court and the discriminatory body, as well as the legislator's authority to consider tax collection decisions and administrative prosecution.

Accordingly, these last two jurisdictions are more administrative than a criminal nature, and the jurisdiction of the Customs Court is therefore logically and realistically considered.

Second: disputes under the law on the value of the property and its benefits, as for registration taxes, which are a form of trading tax, which the Iraqi legislator called the fee, and some felt that this designation was received by mistake, as it is a financial obligation that is collected by force and carries the meaning of tax ⁽¹²⁰⁾.

The law on the assessment of the value of the property clarified the mechanism for objecting to this type of tax, where it authorized the Real Estate Registration Department and the party for which it was disclosed or at its request to object to the decisions to impose the tax on the value of the property estimated by the Disclosure Committee, to a committee named the Objection Committee, where it is formed by the Minister of Finance and headed by a judge and a representative of the Ministry of Finance and a technical officer and is competent to consider objections to the statements contained in the disclosure minutes in seven days of the date of the organization of the disclosure record, the person in charge of challenging the decisions of the Disclosure Committee after paying fees and taxes, and the decisions issued by the Committee are categorical and not subject to appeal to any party ⁽¹²¹⁾.

The second requirement: Legal adaptation of decisions to challenge tax estimates

Opinions differed on the legal adaptation of these entities whether they are administrative bodies with jurisdiction or judicial bodies, and we will show it through the legal nature of the decision to adjudicate the objection to tax decisions in Iraqi legislation, branch two branches of this requirement as follows:

Section one

The judicial nature of the decision to adjudicate the objection to tax decisions

A team of jurists argued that the tax committees competent to look at tax disputes in Iraq are judicial bodies, considering that the Real Estate Tax Office is a body of administrative justice and that it is used by both the taxpayer and the tax administration when it is found that the tax law was not applied properly, causing harm to one or both of them ⁽¹²²⁾.

Another group of jurists did not recognize that tax committees were judicial committees based on the real estate tax office, yet considered the discriminatory and appeals committees to be independent judicial bodies.

The administrative nature of the judicial jurisdiction of decisions issued by tax committees:

adopted by a few jurists, they considered that the tax committees competent to deal with tax disputes are administrative, but at the same time have jurisdiction, they are competent to adjudicate all tax disputes between the persons in charge and the tax authority, in the same way as the ordinary courts, and thus are not subject to tax administration and do not comply with the application of their instructions if they are within the scope of the legal texts while another group has been established. This status is applied to both the appellate committees and the commission of excellence, on the basis that it is formed under the chairmanship of a judge, and has functional independence from tax administration.

Section two

The administrative nature of the decision to adjudicate the objection to tax decisions

Some jurists criticized the trend that tax committees were judicial, and went further, considering that tax committees were purely administrative bodies. Others felt that the appellate committees had administrative authority, even if they were chaired by judges, and justified this by the fact that the appointment of judges to these committees is because of their legal experience, which is the same for the financial officials who depend on them according to their experience in financial matters, but concerning the real estate tax office, it represents an administrative body embodied by a body of employees, entrusted by the legislator to monitor the application of the law. Another group of jurists argued that the appellate and discriminatory committees provided for in the Income Tax Act were purely administrative entities because their members were the administrative staff. Others also went on to consider the decisions of the tax commissions as judicial decisions. Accordingly, we believe that decisions issued by tax committees are administrative decisions of judicial nature.

The third topic

Procedural framework for administrative challenge to tax assessment decisions

Tax legislation usually contains provisions dealing with administrative appeals procedures in tax assessment decisions, which may not prejudice the right of the taxpayer to resort to appealing, which is considered the most important constitutional guarantee that protects his rights and freedoms.

Therefore, no decision by the tax administration should be shielded from objection and appeal, as the legislator provided for the resolution of tax disputes between individuals and the tax administration in an administrative manner, to establish trust between the individuals in charge and the tax administration, and must precede the stage of an administrative challenge to tax assessment decisions of the tax administration before the parties resort to justice, making the appeal route obligatory.

Through this research, we will examine the administrative appeals procedures for tax assessment decisions in the **first requirement**, while in the **second requirement** we will address the administrative appeals procedures for tax assessment decisions in comparative legislation.

The first requirement: Administrative appeals against the decision to estimate income tax

The Iraqi legislature, like the harsh legislation, allows the person who did not approve of the authority's decision

In the imposition of the tax, he should initiate an objection before the same body that issued the decision to estimate income and tax, which is called a grievance. The appeal means that the stakeholder submits to the source or president of the decision a request to withdraw or amend the decision. Income tax is a direct tax in Iraq, which is imposed under Law No. (113) of 1983. Jurists and tax legislation differed on the definition of income tax and were not given a specific definition of that tax, but merely referred to the components of the tax pot, but for the Iraqi legislator, income was defined as "the revenue of the net taxpayer obtained from the sources provided for in Article II of this Act.". Tax legislation, particularly Iraqi legislation, has also regulated procedures for submitting objections to discretionary income tax decisions issued by the tax administration against taxpayers, as well as the competent authority to consider the objection and its conditions, there is a certain period to submit an objection to the income tax decision administratively, and many provisions stipulated in the Iraqi tax legislation to regulate the appeal and administrative objection to tax decisions. Accordingly, the requirement divides the two branches, **the first section** of the objection before the Finance Committee, and **the second section to object before the appeals committees.**

Section one

Objection before the Finance Committee

The Iraqi Income Tax Act provided for the right of the taxpayer to object to the financial committee's decision, but it required several conditions to be met so that the taxpayer could object to the finance committee's decision, the most important of which were: ⁽³⁾

1. The objection to the final decision submitted by the taxpayer must be issued by the financial authority, as the objection to reserve assessment decisions shall be made only after it becomes final.
2. The objection is only after -tax, but it may be on the decision to impose the tax and the decision to estimate the income.
3. It is not permissible to object to the tax assessment decision after the approval of the reconciliation settlement.
4. The objection should take place after the decision of the Financial Authority has been reported.
5. The objection must also be written.
6. The objection must take place within the legal period specified in the law, and Iraqi law has required that the objection be submitted within (21) days of the date of notification of the decision.
7. The objection must include the reasons for the objection as well as the amendment to be made.
8. The objecting person must pay the tax due.

Referring to the provisions of Iraqi legislation, we believe that the legislator must submit the objection within the legal time limit, as the taxpayer must submit the objection to the tax administration within a day of the date of notification.

Concerning the authority competent to consider the objection to the Iraqi Income Tax Act, the financial authority that issued the objectionable decision, but the consideration of the objection is one of the functions of the financial body that issued that decision, giving the taxpayer the right to object to the body that issued the decision, to facilitate the individuals in charge, especially if they are residing far from the chamber that issued the decision, and not to miss the time limit for submitting the objection.

After the taxpayer submits the objection to the income tax decision before the relevant party, the objection submitted by the objector shall be as follows: ⁽⁵⁾

First: Objection

Iraqi legislation stipulates that if the financial authorities find that the objector has not clarified the reasons for submitting the objection, his objection is rejected, and the decision taken by the Financial Authority shall be a definitive decision that is not subject to appeal, either by appeal or by discrimination, and the same when the objector fails to pay the tax within the specified period of the objection, in which case the financial authority refrains from considering the objection and the consequences of rejecting that objection after the expiry of the specified legal period, which The tax must be paid and the estimate becomes absolute .

The person in charge of submitting the objection may submit the objection after the legal period specified for the objection, nor will it provide convincing reasons that the Financial Authority has not been satisfied with and has not agreed to extend the specified period, and here, in this case the authority concerned will reject the objection, and the Iraqi legislator considered it a definite decision that is not subject to appeal, either by appeal or by discrimination.

Second: Acceptance of the objection in Iraqi legislation: If the Malian authority becomes clear that the objection has fulfilled all the conditions of its validity, in which case the competent official will discuss the objection, and if the objector is unable to convince the financial authority of the validity of his claim, such as

being unable to submit adequate books and documents to support his objection, then the objection is received, but it must justify the reasons for its objection and here the objector has the right to appeal the decision of the Financial Committee to the appeal committees because the decision of the Financial Committee containing the objection to reject the objection Does not make the decision made definitively.

Section 2

Objection to appeals committees

Iraqi legislation provides for the right of the taxpayer opposed to the income tax decision to object to the appeals committees, which consists of two committees: the Public Audit Committee, which is composed of two members, appointed by the Financial Authority, and two other members selected by the Financial Authority from the nomination lists submitted by the Chamber of Commerce, and which is specialized in considering objections by persons residing within the city limits. The Special Audit Committee consists of three senior officials of the Ministry of Finance and is competent to consider objections made by individuals in charge who prefer to submit them before the Special Audit Committee rather than the Public Audit Committee, but are obliged to pay a certain fee when submitting their objection, and to note that the decisions of public and private audit committees are strict in terms of the amount of tax estimate and taxable income.

Decisions that have already been challenged are the same as those that may be appealed to appeal to appeals committees, but about decisions of the financial authority that have missed the prescribed period of the objection, they are categorically not subject to appeal, as the appeal is required to be written, to be made after the objection has been rejected and then submitted within the specified legal period, as well as to require the taxpayer to pay the tax. Concerning the appeal decision, either the appeal would be dismissed, the appellant's assessment upheld or increased, and the Appeal Committee might decide to reduce the appellant's assessment, and the decision could be made to uphold the contempt and annul the appellant's estimate.

Discrimination of the appeal decision

Discrimination is the last way to appeal, through which decisions issued by appeal committees are distinguished, and decisions issued by the authority on discretion are not directly discriminatory before their appeal and appeal, and the Iraqi legislator has not made all appeal decisions appealable to the discriminatory body, but rather singled out decisions in which the amount of tax exceeds 10,000 dinars, and each appeal holder has the right to discriminate before the discriminatory body, and the acceptance of discrimination is required to be available to the discriminatory body. There are several conditions, including that the application for discrimination is written, that the amount of tax be more than 10,000 dinars, that the legal period specified be submitted, and that the law required that the discrimination of the appeal decision be accepted by the taxpayer to pay the fee to the discriminatory party.

The Iraqi tax legislator has been given the power to hear discriminatory appeals in decisions on appeals committees to the Discriminatory Tax Authority, which is formed at the headquarters of the General Tax Authority, where it is chaired by a judge of the Court of Cassation with two members of the General Managers of the Ministry of Finance, as well as a member of the Iraqi Federation of Industries, and another member of the Federation of the Iraqi Chamber of Commerce, who are appointed by the Ministry of Finance. The decision of the discriminatory body shall be either to annul the privileged decision when it violates the rules of jurisdiction when the decision of the Appeal Committee is issued contrary to the rules of spatial or functional jurisdiction , or to issue the decision of the discriminatory body considering the distinguished decision was made contrary to the rules of procedure to be followed when issuing an appeal decision, and as the decision may be issued with the support of the privileged decision or amend the privileged decision (17).

The second requirement: Administrative appeals against the decision to estimate the property tax

Iraqi tax legislation did not provide for the formation of objection bodies, but rather the person in charge of the objection directly before the financial authority, i.e. before the same party that carried out the tax assessment procedures, informed him of the estimate, or before any department of the General Tax Authority and within (21) twenty-one days of the date of his notification indicating the reasons for his objection, and the amendment he requests and must submit to the Financial Authority the books, records and data relating to his income to prove his objection, on the other hand (18).

We note that the period of objection is lower than other comparative legislation, and Iraqi law has given the Financial Authority the acceptance of the objection after the specified period if it is satisfied that the objector has not been able because of coercion, but concerning the effects of the objection submitted to the financial authority, the financial authority has the right to accept or reject the objection, and there may be an agreement between the taxpayer and the financial authority to estimate the income, so that this correction, or the agreement, is decisive for the dispute once and for all.

The right of the objecting official to appeal to the Appeals Committee shall be overturned, as stipulated in article (34) of the Iraqi Tax Code in force, but if the Financial Authority rejects the objection, it is an administrative decision, but it is inconclusive to the dispute because the person in charge can appeal against the decision before an appeals committee, and thus discriminate before a discriminatory body, and this committee and the body that was mentioned earlier as bodies subsequently formed and the method of objection before this committee or body (19).

1- In the districts of provincial centers: financial officer - president - employee - member - two real estate experts - two members.

2. In other districts: the acting, or financial officer - president - financial officer. Two expert members of real estate - organic.

The applicant submits the objection request to the Audit Committee through the Financial Authority within not more than 30 days from the date it reports the report, at which point the audit committee when considering objections, must take an experienced opinion on real estate matters, conduct investigations and request the papers it deems necessary, disclose the property, respond to the objection, or make a change of judgment, and must report its decision to the taxpayer and the financial authority, and then act on the audit committee's assessment from the date of the objection. If the person in charge of the audit committee's decision is satisfied, he must pay the tax, but if he is not convinced, the law has guaranteed him the right to appeal to another committee equivalent to the discriminatory body in the Income Tax Act (The Real Estate Tax Office), as we will address it later.

We can say that despite the objectionable body presided over by a judge and adjudicating disputes, it is linked to the tax administration, making it an administrative body of the Customs Department, so that the provision and the deduction are the same, the body does not have full independence, and the end is unfair to the taxpayer, especially if we find that there is a special customs court, but its jurisdiction is very specific. In the tax area and within the scope of the applicable Iraqi property tax law, the person in charge whose objection was rejected by the Audit Committee, or made a change in the estimate of objection (discrimination) to the Real Estate Tax Office to the decision of the Audit Committee, or the procedures of the financial authority, as well as the law authorized the financial authority to object to the decisions of the Real Estate Tax Commission, if the following objection requirements are met:

The decision of the Audit Committee, or the procedures of the financial authority. The objection must be within 30 days of the date of notification of the 229 legitimate excuses unless the duration of the objection has not expired.

- The fiscal year should not have ended if the taxpayer was not informed

- The objector must pay a fee of 2,500,500 Iraqi dinars to the General Tax Authority Fund.

As noted in the Income Tax Act, the financial authority does not pay any fee if it objects, and if the above conditions are met in the objection, the Court shall consider the dispute before it and issue its decision, which does not depart from the following cases: the annulment of the audit committee's decision, or the actions of the financial authority. The decision of the audit committee, or the procedures of the financial authority, is supported, and the decision of the Diwan shall be absolutely (categorical), and if the property is required to be disclosed, the taxpayer or the financial authority shall be summoned. It should be noted that the discriminatory body in the Income Tax Act and the Real Estate Tax Office in the Applicable Property Tax Act are also administrative bodies formed by order of the Minister of Financial Authority, and the above shall be withdrawn.

The objection to the decisions issued by the Administration before the same body should also be the source of the decision as a first stage, as the justice system requires that the objection of one side be considered by another, which had no say in the first decision. In doing so, we note that the Iraqi tax legislature has not guaranteed the right to litigate, as stipulated in article (19) paragraph III since constitutions, as a rule, provide for the right of everyone to resort to litigation, as confirmed by the Iraqi Constitution in the article (100), which prohibited the fortification of any act or decision of occupation, and in this situation, all these committees and their decisions are flagrantly contrary to the Constitution (11).

Conclusion

The decision to estimate income tax and the ways to object to it is one of the most important burdens facing the tax administration, and the taxpayers, because of the importance of taxes, considering taxes from revenues to states and is of great importance in providing the state treasury with the funds necessary to be able to achieve its objectives in all areas through the tax system it chooses to implement its fiscal and tax policy, and due to this importance, legislation has approved various means, and guarantees that facilitate the task of the administration Tax, concerning the assessment of tax on taxpayers taking into account what guarantees their rights without abuse or waste. In this study, we went on to examine the decision to estimate income tax and how it is challenged by reviewing the tax base, which includes the article that is the subject of the assessment that creates tax disputes, the means to prove the tax burden, and how to resort to objections during its stages towards the broad powers of the tax administration to estimate, thereby achieving protection for individuals in the face of

these powers, whether through administrative or judicial objections. We have also clarified the methods of administrative appeal in the discretionary decisions of the tax and the provisions of this appeal as organized by Iraqi tax legislation, as well as the procedures for judicial appeal to the decisions of the tax commissions in Iraq and some comparative legislation and the differences between these procedures and the stages of litigation before the relevant authorities.

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Article II of article II of iraq's amended constitution of 2005.

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